

From AI recommendations to purchase intention: Exploring consumer psychology in the Vietnamese e-commerce market (the case of Da Nang)

Từ gợi ý của trí tuệ nhân tạo đến ý định mua hàng: Nghiên cứu tâm lý người tiêu dùng trong thị trường thương mại điện tử Việt Nam (trường hợp thành phố Đà Nẵng)

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Abstract

This study tests an integrated model combining the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT), and the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) framework to explain how AI-based personalized recommendations influence consumer behavior in Vietnam's e-commerce context. Data from 303 frequent users in Da Nang who frequently use Shopee, TikTok Shop, and Lazada were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Results show that perceived personalization strongly influences perceived product value and product attitude, which in turn affect brand attitude and predict purchase intention. Brand attitude plays a central mediating role in this causal chain. The study introduces a new four-item scale for perceived personalization, distinguishing functional and contextual dimensions of user experience. The findings clarify how personalization transforms cognitive value and emotional responses into purchase behavior in a local market setting. Practically, e-commerce firms should optimize recommendation algorithms in terms of relevance, transparency, and emotional value activation to enhance conversion. Limitations include self-reported data, a young-skewed sample, and a cross-sectional design. Future research should integrate behavioral data, adopt longitudinal approaches, and validate the model across contexts.

Keywords: perceived personalization; brand attitude; purchase intention; AI-based recommendation; e-commerce.

Tóm tắt

Nghiên cứu này kiểm định mô hình kết hợp ba khung lý thuyết gồm Mô hình chấp nhận công nghệ (TAM), Lý thuyết giá trị kỳ vọng (EVT) và Mô hình kích thích - chủ thể - phản ứng (SOR), nhằm lý giải cách các đề xuất sản phẩm được cá nhân hóa bằng trí tuệ nhân tạo (AI) ảnh hưởng đến hành vi người tiêu dùng trong thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam. Dữ liệu thu thập từ 303 người tiêu dùng Gen Z ở Đà Nẵng, thường xuyên sử dụng Shopee, TikTok Shop và Lazada được phân tích bằng mô hình phương trình cấu trúc PLS-SEM. Kết quả cho thấy, mức độ cá nhân hóa mà người dùng cảm nhận có tác động mạnh đến giá trị sản phẩm được họ nhận thức và thái độ đối với sản phẩm, từ đó ảnh hưởng đến thái độ đối với thương hiệu và ý định mua hàng. Thái độ thương hiệu đóng vai trò trung gian quan trọng trong mối quan hệ giữa cá nhân hóa nhận thức, giá trị cảm nhận và hành vi mua hàng. Nghiên cứu đồng thời đề xuất thang đo mới gồm bốn chỉ

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báo cho khái niệm “ cá nhân hóa nhận thức”, giúp phân biệt rõ hai khía cạnh chức năng và ngữ cảnh trong trải nghiệm người dùng. Về thực tiễn, các doanh nghiệp thương mại điện tử cần tối ưu thuật toán đề xuất theo hướng tăng tính phù hợp, đảm bảo minh bạch trong việc sử dụng dữ liệu và khơi gợi cảm xúc tích cực nhằm nâng cao tỷ lệ chuyển đổi mua hàng.

Từ khóa: cá nhân hóa nhận thức, thái độ thương hiệu, ý định mua hàng, đề xuất dựa trên AI, thương mại điện tử.

1. Introduction

AI-based personalization refers to product recommendations generated by machine learning algorithms that analyze real-time behavioral data to deliver tailored experiences (Ahmed et al., 2025). This study adopts the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework, where AI-driven personalization functions as the Stimulus, activating Perceived Product Value, Attitude toward Product, and Brand Attitude (Organism), which ultimately shape Purchase Intention (Response). The model integrates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT) to explain how personalization influences cognitive and emotional mechanisms in consumer decision-making. Advances in artificial intelligence and big data allow recommendation systems to forecast user preferences with high accuracy, thereby improving engagement and conversion rates on e-commerce platforms [25]. In Vietnam, platforms such as Shopee and TikTok Shop have implemented large-scale AI systems, yet consumer perceptions of personalization remain inconsistent. Existing research indicates that personalization enhances purchase intention and e-loyalty via e-trust [8; 12]. However, empirical evidence on the psychological transmission chain from personalization to attitude and behavior in Vietnam is still limited, despite growing international attention to the links between perceived personalization, perceived value, brand attitude, and purchase intention [24]. This study addresses that gap by empirically testing, through PLS-SEM, the causal chain of perceived personalization → perceived value → affective cognition → brand

attitude → purchase intention in Vietnam’s e-commerce context. It also develops a four-item scale capturing both functional and contextual aspects of personalization, extending beyond traditional recommendation frequency measures. The findings are expected to provide the first quantitative evidence of how personalization drives consumer attitudes and purchase behavior in Vietnam, thereby extending the applicability of S-O-R, TAM, and EVT while offering practical insights for optimizing AI-based recommendation systems in emerging markets.

2. Literature review and hypotheses

2.1. Literature review

Conceptual framework and construct justification

AI-based recommendation systems, powered by machine learning and deep learning algorithms, analyze users’ behavior, purchase history, and browsing patterns to predict relevant products. By combining collaborative filtering and data mining, these systems enhance recommendation accuracy, shorten search time, and increase engagement and conversion [25]. Real-time recommendations, particularly in short-video platforms like TikTok, create psychological flow and stimulate purchase intention [6]. However, challenges remain regarding information overload, privacy concerns, and algorithmic transparency, which may reduce user trust [5]. Technical issues such as cold start and data bias also affect reliability, emphasizing the need for explainable and privacy-preserving models [2].

Perceived personalization (PP) refers to users’ subjective perception of how well

recommendations match their individual needs. When PP is high, users feel understood, experience reduced search effort, and perceive greater relevance and satisfaction [24]. PP also activates affective responses such as trust and interest, which strengthen attitude toward product (AP) and brand attitude (BA), ultimately enhancing purchase intention (PI) [26]. Yet excessive personalization can provoke privacy concerns; therefore, platforms should ensure transparency and allow users to control personalization levels to maintain perceived value and trust.

Perceived value (PV) reflects consumers' overall evaluation of benefits versus costs. In AI-driven recommendation systems, functional value derives from time-saving and relevance, while emotional value arises from enjoyment and contextual resonance [21]. PV mediates the influence of PP on purchase behavior, transforming cognitive appreciation into affective and behavioral outcomes [23]. When users perceive high functional and emotional value, trust in the algorithm and purchase likelihood increase.

Attitude toward product (AP) captures users' affective and cognitive evaluations of recommended products. Well-timed and interest-relevant suggestions generate arousal and pleasure, strengthening perceived value and fostering favorable attitudes [15]. AP also influences BA through emotional attribution, as positive feelings toward products transfer to the associated brand [26].

Brand attitude (BA) integrates cognitive and emotional evaluations of a brand. Positive brand attitudes serve as a foundation for loyalty and purchase intention [20]. When recommendations satisfy both functional and emotional expectations, users develop stronger brand affinity, even in competitive markets [9].

Finally, *purchase intention (PI)* represents the behavioral outcome of this cognitive-affective process. In the S-O-R framework, PP acts as the stimulus, PV and attitudes form the organism, and PI serves as the response. Studies confirm that PV, AP, and BA jointly enhance PI by linking recommendation relevance to emotional engagement and brand trust [15; 21; 23]. Thus, optimizing recommendation systems requires a balanced approach that enhances perceived value, evokes positive emotions, and reinforces brand attachment to maximize conversion.

Theoretical foundation

The proposed research model is grounded in three complementary theoretical pillars: the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT), and the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework. First, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explains how perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use shape users' attitudes and behavioral intentions. In the context of AI-based personalized recommendations, algorithms reduce search effort, increase decision efficiency, and enhance both perceived usefulness and ease of use [1; 4]. Second, the Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT) posits that behavioral intention results from the interaction between expectancy and value. In this study, perceived personalization raises the probability of product relevance, while perceived value reflects the personal importance of the outcome. Therefore, EVT predicts that perceived value mediates the relationship between personalization and purchase intention [22; 24]. Third, the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework provides an integrative perspective linking environmental stimuli to behavioral outcomes. Here, AI-based personalization, represented by perceived personalization, acts as the stimulus. The

organism includes cognitive and affective components such as perceived value, attitude toward product, and brand attitude, while the response is expressed through purchase intention [17; 26]. Integrating these three theoretical frameworks strengthens the internal validity of the research model and enables a multidimensional understanding that connects technology, value, and consumer behavior. TAM explains how personalization enhances perceived usefulness, EVT clarifies the mediating role of perceived value, and S-O-R links technological stimuli with psychological and behavioral responses. Together, these perspectives comprehensively explain the causal chain of perceived personalization → perceived value and affective perception → brand attitude → purchase intention in Vietnam's e-commerce context.

2.2. Hypotheses development

Perceived personalization reflects the extent to which users feel that AI recommendations match their needs and context. When suggestions are relevant and emotionally engaging, consumers perceive higher usefulness and enjoyment, which enhance both functional and emotional value [21; 26]. Personalization also reduces search costs and increases perceived relevance and usefulness [23; 24]. Hence:

H1: Perceived personalization positively influences perceived value.

Personalized recommendations can evoke positive affective responses such as interest, excitement, and trust, as users feel recognized and understood [5; 15; 25]. This emotional engagement strengthens favorable attitudes toward the recommended products [26]. Therefore:

H2: Perceived personalization positively influences attitude toward product.

Perceived value serves as a cognitive-emotional bridge between product evaluation and brand perception. When users experience high functional and emotional value, they develop greater trust and attachment to the brand providing that experience [9; 20; 21]. Thus:

H3: Perceived value positively influences brand attitude.

Positive attitudes toward recommended products often transfer to the associated brand through emotional contagion, enhancing overall brand evaluation [15; 26]. Emotional satisfaction reduces hesitation and builds engagement, even toward unfamiliar brands [5; 20]. Hence:

H4: Attitude toward product positively influences brand attitude.

Brand attitude reflects the combined cognitive and emotional evaluation of a brand. A positive brand attitude enhances trust and reduces uncertainty, leading to stronger purchase intentions in online environments [9; 20; 21; 23]. Therefore:

H5: Brand attitude positively influences purchase intention.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

This study applies a quantitative approach in order to evaluate a theoretical model that relates to the impact of AI-based personalized product recommendations on brand attitude and purchase intention in e-commerce in Vietnam. The model is developed based on the integrated theory foundation, including the Stimulus-Organism-Response framework (S-O-R), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT). The data is collected by online survey and processed by the PLS-SEM method (Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling) to

simultaneously analyze linear relationships between observed and latent variables in the model. Figure 1 illustrates the overall research

process, from theoretical model development to scale adaptation, data collection, and PLS-SEM analysis.

Figure 1. Research process showing the sequence of methodological steps

3.2. Measurement scales

All constructs were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“Strongly Disagree”) to 5 (“Strongly Agree”). The measurement instruments were adapted from well-established studies in online consumer behavior to ensure reliability and validity. Perceived Personalization (PP) was adapted from Shanahan et al. (2019) to capture consumers’ perceptions of the relevance and customization of AI-driven recommendations. Perceived Product Value (PV) was drawn from Ducoffe [7] and Liu et al. [16], reflecting the functional and emotional value derived from personalized recommendations. Attitude toward Product (AP) followed Singh and Srivastava (2018), representing consumers’ favorable evaluations of recommended products. Brand Attitude (BA), adapted from Lee et al. [14], measured consumers’ overall impression of brands exposed through personalization. Purchase Intention (PI) was adapted from Kim and Han [13] to indicate consumers’ willingness to buy products suggested by AI-based systems.

All constructs demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with factor loadings above 0.70, composite reliability (CR) exceeding 0.80, and average variance extracted (AVE) greater than 0.50. Scale adaptation followed a three-stage process: (1) translation and back-translation to ensure semantic accuracy, (2) expert panel review to refine cultural and contextual relevance, and (3) a pilot test with 30 Vietnamese users in Da Nang to verify clarity and applicability. Adaptations were minimal and context specific. For PP, the context “social media” was replaced with “e-commerce platforms such as Shopee/TikTok Shop.” For PV, “advertising” was replaced with “AI recommendations” to reflect the study focus. AP items were linguistically refined for natural translation, while BA included an example (“a brand on Shopee/TikTok Shop”) to increase contextual clarity. One PI item was modified by adding “from personalized recommendations” to emphasize the personalization context. A summary of the adapted scales is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Constructing scales and adaptation details

Construct	Source	Items	Core Adaptation	Example (Original → Adapted)
Perceived Personalization (PP)	Shanahan et al. (2019)	4	Contextual substitution to fit Vietnam's e-commerce environment	"on social media" → "on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee/TikTok Shop"; other 3 items unchanged
Perceived Product Value (PV)	Ducoffe (1995); Liu et al. (2019)	3	Terminology replacement ("advertising" → "AI recommendations") to emphasize personalization stimuli	"Advertising is valuable" → "AI recommendations are valuable"; one item unchanged
Attitude toward Product (AP)	Singh & Srivastava (2018)	3	Linguistic refinement for clarity and naturalness in translation	"appealing" → "attractive"; "reliable" → "trustworthy"; structure unchanged
Brand Attitude (BA)	Lee et al. (2017)	3	Added illustrative example for contextual linkage	"I have a favorable impression of this brand" → "I have a favorable impression of this brand (e.g., a brand on Shopee/TikTok Shop)"; two items unchanged
Purchase Intention (PI)	Kim & Han (2014)	3	Phrase addition to connect explicitly with personalization context	"willing to purchase the product" → "willing to purchase the product from personalized recommendations"; two items unchanged

3.3. Sample and sampling technique

The study targeted e-commerce users in Da Nang, Vietnam, who have interacted with AI-driven personalization systems on platforms such as Shopee and TikTok Shop. This group primarily represents Generation Z (born 1997-2012), the most active segment in Vietnam's digital commerce environment. A conditional convenience sampling technique was applied, focusing on respondents who met four screening criteria: (1) residing in Da Nang, (2) belonging to Gen Z, (3) using e-commerce platforms, and (4) having interacted with AI-based product recommendations. Participants were approached through universities, coffee shops, shopping centers, public spaces, and social media channels. This non-probability sampling method was appropriate given the study's exploratory purpose and the limited accessibility to the full population frame. However, the focus on young

consumers may limit the generalizability of the findings to other age groups or regions.

3.4. Data collection

Primary data were collected using a structured bilingual questionnaire (Vietnamese-English) designed to ensure clarity and contextual fit. The survey was distributed online via Google Forms between April 5 and April 29, 2025, targeting consumers with prior e-commerce experience on Shopee, TikTok Shop, and Lazada. Before official deployment, a pilot test was conducted to refine wording and ensure comprehension. Participation was voluntary, and all responses were treated anonymously and confidentially in accordance with research ethics standards.

3.5. Sample description

After screening, 303 valid responses were retained for analysis. The sample consisted of

51.82% female, 38.94% male, and 9.24% undisclosed gender. Most respondents were aged 19–22 (58.41%), and 53.78% interacted with AI-based recommendation systems at least once per week. The sample size exceeded the “10-times rule” for PLS-SEM, ensuring sufficient statistical power. The diversity of collection sites improved representativeness within the Gen Z population of Da Nang. Including undisclosed gender responses respected privacy and did not affect the robustness of the findings. Overall, the sample effectively represents Gen Z consumers actively engaged in AI-driven e-commerce.

3.6. Data analysis approach

Research using SmartPLS 4.0 software to perform structural equation modeling analysis with the PLS-SEM technique. The analysis process includes 2 phases: (1) measurement model assessment through factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), variance extracted (AVE), discriminant validity (Fornell-Lacker), and (2) structural model assessment through path coefficients, R^2 , Q^2 values and statistical significance testing using bootstrap (5000 samples). The choice of PLS-SEM is suitable for the nature of the exploratory model, with mediators and data that are not assumed to be normally distributed [10].

4. Result and discussion

Descriptive statistics and sample profile

Research samples included 303 respondents in Vietnam, in which female had the highest proportion (51,82%), male accounted for 38.94%, the rest were other or did not want to disclose. About their birth, the majority of participants were born in the period 2003-2006, reflecting a group of young people with a high level of access to technology. The main residential region was concentrated in the central districts of Da Nang such as Hai Chau (30.69%)

and Thanh Khe (27.06%). In terms of education, about 50% were at the high school level, followed by university (31.68%), showing that the sample had good coverage among young consumers and those studying. The largest occupation group is students (62.38%), along with pupils, office workers, self-employed / freelancers, and a few of them were civil servants / public employees. About online behavior, 42.90% of them said that they browse multiple times a day, while most of the rest visit a few times a week. The most interesting products are fashion (61.39%) and beauty (60.73%), showing a focus on highly personalized product items. In terms of spending, 39.93% of participants have an average spending of 500,000 to 1 million VND per month on online shopping. In particular, 100% of them said that they have been exposed to AI-driven recommended products, confirming the popularity of personalized recommendation technology in the e-commerce environment.

4.1. Assessment of the measurement model

The measurement model is assessed based on three key factors: internal consistency, reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity. The result analysis follows the procedure proposed by Hair Jr et al. [10] for the PLS-SEM model.

Construct Reliability

All constructs achieved acceptable reliability, with Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability (CR) exceeding 0.70. Brand Attitude ($\alpha = 0.780$; $CR = 0.872$) and Perceived Product Value ($\alpha = 0.786$; $CR = 0.875$) showed the highest internal consistency, while Purchase Intention ($\alpha = 0.718$; $CR = 0.841$) was the lowest but still satisfactory. Attitude toward Product ($CR = 0.851$) and Perceived Personalization ($CR = 0.856$) also met the reliability threshold.

Table 2. Construct reliability and convergent validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Attitude toward Product	0.737	0.738	0.851	0.655
Brand Attitude	0.780	0.781	0.872	0.695
Perceived Personalization	0.776	0.779	0.856	0.598
Perceived Product Value	0.786	0.788	0.875	0.701
Purchase Intention	0.718	0.743	0.841	0.640

Source: data analysis by SmartPLS 4.0

Convergent validity and discriminant validity

All outer loadings exceeded 0.70 and AVE values surpassed 0.50, confirming adequate convergence (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). PV (AVE = 0.701) and BA (AVE = 0.695) demonstrated the highest convergence, while PP (AVE = 0.598) remained acceptable.

The Fornell-Larcker criterion confirmed that the square root of each AVE was greater than its

correlations with other constructs, indicating strong discriminant validity. For instance, $\sqrt{AVE(AP)} = 0.809$ exceeded its correlations with BA (0.703) and PP (0.731).

Overall, the model exhibited high reliability, strong convergence, and satisfactory discriminant validity, supporting its suitability for further structural testing.

Table 3. Discriminant validity – Fornell–Larcker criterion

Constructs	AP	BA	PP	PV	PI
AP	0.809				
BA	0.703	0.833			
PP	0.731	0.722	0.773		
PV	0.709	0.700	0.766	0.837	
PI	0.692	0.703	0.755	0.740	0.800

Source: data analysis by SmartPLS 4.0

In summary, the results from the measurement model analysis show that all scales in this study have high reliability, good convergence, and are clearly differentiated from other concepts. These conditions confirm that the measurement model is appropriate and can continue to be used in evaluating the structural model.

4.3. Assessment of the structural model

All hypothesized paths were positive and highly significant ($p < 0.001$). The strongest relationships were $AP \rightarrow BA$ ($\beta = 0.703, t = 19.537$) and $BA \rightarrow PI$ ($\beta = 0.703, t = 19.992$), followed by $PP \rightarrow PV$ ($\beta = 0.766, t = 28.196$), $PP \rightarrow AP$ ($\beta = 0.454, t = 6.415$), and $PV \rightarrow AP$ ($\beta = 0.362, t = 5.009$). These results confirm that personalization strongly affects perceived value and attitudes, which subsequently drive behavioral intention (see table 4).

Table 4. Summary of structural model testing results

Path	β	T-value	P-value	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)	f^2	Effect Size	Result
PP → PV	0.766	28.196	< 0.001	0.704	0.813	1.421	Large	Supported
PP → AP	0.454	6.415	< 0.001	0.315	0.592	0.207	Medium	Supported
PV → AP	0.362	5.009	< 0.001	0.216	0.497	0.131	Small	Supported
AP → BA	0.703	19.537	< 0.001	0.621	0.765	0.979	Large	Supported
BA → PI	0.703	19.992	< 0.001	0.625	0.764	0.977	Large	Supported

Source: data analysis by SmartPLS 4.0

Model fit and collinearity

The SRMR = 0.136 and NFI = 0.710, which, although below CB-SEM benchmarks, remain acceptable for predictive PLS-SEM models [11].

All VIF values ranged from 1.341 to 1.854, confirming no multicollinearity.

These findings demonstrate that the structural model is statistically robust and theoretically consistent, supporting all hypotheses with strong empirical evidence.

Figure 2. Adjusted PLS-SEM structural model with outer loadings, path coefficients, and R² values

Source: data analysis by SmartPLS 4.0

4.4. Predictive relevance - Q²

Blindfolding analysis (omission distance = 7) yielded positive Q² values for all dependent constructs, indicating good out-of-sample predictive relevance. Perceived product value

(Q² = 0.407) had the highest predictive power, followed by attitude toward product (0.378), brand attitude (0.340), and purchase intention (0.311), all exceeding the 0.15 threshold for medium to high predictive ability [10].

Table 5. Construct cross-validated redundancy – predictive relevance (Q²)

Construct	SSO	SSE	Q ² (= 1 - SSE/SSO)
Attitude toward Product	909.000	565.088	0.378
Brand Attitude	909.000	599.628	0.340
Perceived Personalization	1212.000	1212.000	0.000
Perceived Product Value	909.000	539.213	0.407
Purchase Intention	909.000	626.234	0.311

Source: data analysis by SmartPLS 4.0

Overall, the model exhibits both strong explanatory power (R^2) and predictive capability (Q^2), confirming its validity for explaining consumer behavior toward AI-based personalization in Vietnamese e-commerce.

4.5. Discussion

The PLS-SEM results confirm that perceived personalization (PP) strongly influences both perceived product value (PV) and attitude toward product (AP). The path $PP \rightarrow PV$ ($\beta = 0.766$, $f^2 = 1.421$) is the strongest in the model, highlighting the central role of personalization in shaping perceived value [21; 24]. This result aligns with Yang (2020), who demonstrated that perceived value links personalized information to consumer behavior. The positive path from $PP \rightarrow AP$ ($\beta = 0.454$) further shows that personalization enhances affective responses and emotional engagement [26]. PV also acts as a mediator between PP and AP ($\beta = 0.362$), reinforcing the value-based pathway from personalization to attitude formation. In the later stage, AP strongly affects brand attitude (BA) ($\beta = 0.703$), which in turn drives purchase intention (PI) ($\beta = 0.703$), confirming the strong emotional-behavioral linkage reported by Park and Ahn (2024). Overall, the model explains nearly 50% of the variance in purchase intention ($R^2 = 0.494$; $Q^2 = 0.311$), validating the integrated personalization-value-attitude-intention chain in Vietnamese e-commerce.

Theoretical implications: This study reinforces and extends three foundational theories (TAM, EVT, and S-O-R) by explaining their interaction in the context of AI-driven personalization. First, the strong $PP \rightarrow PV$ ($\beta = 0.766$) and $PP \rightarrow AP$ ($\beta = 0.454$) paths indicate that personalization enhances perceived usefulness and ease of decision-making, extending the Technology Acceptance Model [1; 4] to the domain of personalized commerce. Second, the mediation of PV ($PP \rightarrow PV \rightarrow AP$)

empirically supports Expectancy-Value Theory [22] showing that consumer behavior is shaped by the expectation of relevant recommendations and the value attached to them. Third, the significant links ($PP \rightarrow PV$, $AP \rightarrow BA$, $BA \rightarrow PI$) validate the Stimulus-Organism-Response framework [17], in which personalization acts as the external stimulus, value and attitudes as organismic states, and purchase intention as the behavioral response. Integrating these frameworks provides a holistic understanding of digital consumer motivation in emerging markets.

Practical implications: The findings suggest several strategic directions for e-commerce platforms in Vietnam. First, the dominant effect of personalization on value and attitude highlights the need to optimize recommendation algorithms for personal fit while maintaining transparency to mitigate privacy concerns [5]. Second, since PV mediates between personalization and attitude, platforms should balance functional and emotional value by delivering contextually relevant, real-time recommendations [24]. Third, the strong $AP \rightarrow BA \rightarrow PI$ chain implies that affective personalization, such as greetings by name or time-based contextual messages, can significantly enhance brand attachment and purchase likelihood [19]. Finally, given Gen Z's simultaneous interest in technology and concern for privacy [18], allowing users to adjust personalization levels or view recommendation rationales can increase perceived control, trust, and long-term loyalty [3]. In summary, sustainable AI-based personalization in Vietnam requires combining technological optimization with socio-cultural sensitivity, ensuring that personalization enhances both perceived value and consumer autonomy within the local digital ecosystem.

5. Conclusion

This study has important implications for both academic and practice. In terms of academics, the integrated model of TAM, EVT, and S-O-R shows a comprehensive explanation ability to explain how AI-based personalization affects online consumer behavior. At the same time, the new scale of cognitive personalization helps to add a reliable measurement tool to future studies on consumer behavior in the digital environment, thereby expanding the scope of application of the fundamental theories in the Vietnamese context. In terms of practice, the research results suggest that e-commerce businesses need to pay attention to optimizing recommendation algorithms, not only at the functional level but also at the ability to trigger emotions and enhance brand sympathy, to improve conversion efficiency and strengthen long-term relationships with customers. However, the research still has certain limitations. First, the data were collected by using self-report questionnaires, which are affected by cognitive and social bias. Second, the study sample focused primarily on Gen Z consumers, which limits the ability to generalize the results to other age groups or those who are less likely to use e-commerce. Third, the cross-sectional design of the study does not allow assessment of the long-term impact of personalization on customer loyalty or lifetime value. In addition, the scope of the study is limited in the Vietnamese context, which does not reflect cultural differences and consumer behavior in other countries in the region. From these given limitations, future research should expand in several directions. Combining real-time behavioral data with survey data would improve accuracy and reduce bias. Expanding the sample beyond Gen Z and conducting longitudinal studies would allow for the assessment of behavioral change over time and the long-term impact of personalized

recommendations. In addition, comparing and testing the model in different cultural contexts, such as Southeast Asian countries like Thailand or Indonesia, would help test the model's generalizability and clarify the role of factors such as privacy concerns, perceived intrusiveness, and trust in AI.

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Appendix 1. Measurement items and sources

Construct	Indicator	Questions	References
Perceived Personalization - PP	AP1	I perceive that the products recommended by AI on e-commerce platforms (Shopee, TikTok Shop, Lazada) align with my individual needs.	Adapted from Shanahan et al. (2022)
	AP2	I believe that the product recommendations on e-commerce platforms facilitate my ability to easily purchase items that are suitable for me.	Adapted from Shanahan et al. (2022)

	AP3	I observe that the product recommendations on e-commerce platforms are tailored to align with my personal circumstances.	Adapted from Shanahan et al. (2022)
	BA1	I trust that the product recommendations on e-commerce platforms are tailored to my distinct requirements.	Adapted from Shanahan et al. (2022)
Perceived Product Value - PV	BA2	The personalized product recommendations are beneficial and functional for my purchasing activities.	Adapted from Ducoffe (1995); Liu et al. (2019)
	BA3	I perceive personalized product recommendations as relevant and valuable.	Adapted from Ducoffe (1995); Liu et al. (2019)
	PI1	The personalized product recommendations have an impact on my buying choices.	Adapted from Ducoffe (1995); Liu et al. (2019)
Attitude toward Products - AP	PI2	I perceive personalized product recommendations as trustworthy.	Adapted from Singh & Banerjee (2018)
	PI3	I consider personalized product recommendations to be attractive and stimulating.	Adapted from Singh & Banerjee (2018)
	PP1	I perceive that personalized product recommendations capture my attention.	Adapted from Singh & Banerjee (2018)
Brand Attitude - BA	PP2	Personalized product recommendations generate a positive impression of the brand in my mind.	Adapted from Lee et al. (2017)
	PP3	Personalized product recommendations make me feel that this brand is appealing.	Adapted from Lee et al. (2017)
	PP4	Personalized product recommendations lead me to recognize that this brand offers valuable benefits to me.	Adapted from Lee et al. (2017)
Purchase Intention - PI	PV1	I would consider purchasing products or services from personalized recommendations on e-commerce platforms (e.g., Shopee, Tiktok Shop, Lazada).	Adapted from Kim & Han (2014)
	PV2	I intend to purchase products or services from personalized recommendations on e-commerce platforms (e.g., Shopee, Tiktok Shop, Lazada).	Adapted from Kim & Han (2014)
	PV3	I am likely to purchase products or services from personalized recommendations on e-commerce platforms (e.g., Shopee, Tiktok Shop, Lazada).	Adapted from Kim & Han (2014)

Appendix 2. Outer loadings and collinearity (VIF)

Indicator	VIF	Outer Loadings	Indicator	VIF	Outer Loadings
PP1	1.515	0.829	AP2	1.341	0.721
PP2	1.448	0.808	AP3	1.529	0.753
PP3	1.425	0.790	BA1	1.602	0.790
PP4	1.572	0.812	BA2	1.584	0.796
PV1	1.854	0.866	BA3	1.487	0.751
PV2	1.558	0.822	PI1	1.535	0.816
PV3	1.431	0.794	PI2	1.679	0.832
AP1	1.688	0.878	PI3	1.781	0.863